

PARTICIPATION IN ENSURING THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY, SECONDARY SPECIAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS - AS ONE OF THE MAIN DUTIES OF THE PROSECUTION

Munira Kurbanovna Bobomarova

Independent researcher of The Supreme School OF Judges

Tel: +998 90 960 98 89

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10046131>

Abstract. In this thesis, the main tasks and functions of the prosecutor's office in ensuring the quality and efficiency of education in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions are listed one by one and presented in the form of a short guide for young prosecutors who have just started to work in the field.

Key words: prosecutor's supervision, prosecutor's office, minors, educational institutions, young people, legal framework.

We can learn that education plays a decisive role in shaping societies, empowering individuals and supporting economic well-being from the results of the strategic dialogue on the topic "Development of human capital: education for the future" together with UNICEF, the national movement "Rising".

Agreeing with the words of the former head of the UNICEF representative office in Uzbekistan, Sasha Grauman, "In order for all children to have equal opportunities for quality education, it is necessary to provide such schools with the necessary educational materials and highly qualified teachers [2]", "The development of the country depends on the quality of education for all citizens." it is essential to have an effective education system that provides - we think.

Legal order is one of the main factors in achieving economic well-being and political-legal stability in any country. It is by strengthening the rule of law and legality that the state effectively performs its functions, ensures social justice in society and guarantees the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens.

For example, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, on December 7, 2016, in his holiday greetings dedicated to the 24th anniversary of our Constitution, noted that "the rule of law and ensuring human interests are the guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being" and emphasized the importance of legality [3].

Naturally, the activities of the prosecutor's office are very important in the establishment and implementation of law and order in the society.

F. Rakhimov[4], one of our scientists who explained in detail the directions of the prosecutor's office, said that the directions of the prosecutor's office are divided into two types.

Accordingly, one often overlooked component in maintaining and developing a quality education system is the role of prosecutorial oversight.

The prosecutor's office control over the execution of laws includes the system of special measures aimed at preventing and combating crime and delinquency among young people, as well as creating conditions for proper education and becoming a perfect person.

The objects of prosecutor's supervision in this area include educational institutions, out-of-school educational institutions, guardianship and patronage bodies, medical institutions,

Departments of Ministry of Internal Affairs and Social Security, Social and Legal Assistance Center for Minors, Kindergartens, Kindergartens and Family-type Children's Homes, Children's Towns, local governments, self-governing bodies and the Youth Affairs Agency of Uzbekistan, its territorial units and branches.

The basis of this control is:

- first, education of students of general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions and protection of their rights;
- the second is defined by legislation on combating neglect and delinquency among minors.

The legal documents of both groups are closely related to each other, and the norms mentioned in them are aimed at achieving the goals of educating young people and preventing delinquency and crime among them.

The powers of the prosecutor in the performance of control tasks over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions are wide, and they are related to one or another direction of control areas.

At the same time, the prosecutor is required to be active in the implementation of the powers of the prosecutor, because teenagers are not always able to independently protect and restore their violated rights and legal interests, they need additional guarantees to ensure their rights. According to the order of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2017 No. 139 "On improving the effectiveness of control activities over the implementation of legislation on minors", the following issues are required to be the focus of attention of the prosecutors:

- in the field of education, spiritual and physical development of minors, the establishment of effective and effective control over the unconditional implementation of legislative requirements on education, the implementation of the main principles of state policy in this area, especially the systematic provision of general secondary, as well as secondary special and vocational education ,
- effective control over the attendance of pupils in supervision activities, quality and meaningful organization of educational work and free time of minors, compliance with legal requirements regarding the involvement of minors, especially children in rural areas, in physical education and sports activities, socio-pedagogical rehabilitation of disabled children systematic consideration of their education and full use of the benefits provided for by the law, effective organization of practical training by increasing the responsibility of the heads of secondary, secondary special and vocational educational institutions;
- strengthening control over ensuring that the education system is of a secular nature, ensuring the inevitability of responsibility for attracting minors to religious-extremist or terrorist organizations, providing religious education against the will of their parents or substitutes, violence, cruelty, drug addiction, extremism among minors , taking all necessary measures to prevent the distribution, advertising and display of products that promote terrorism, immorality or immoral lifestyle, including popularization using mass media and the Internet;
- to identify parents who are evading their obligations to financially support, raise and educate their children or do not fulfill them properly, and to carry out preventive measures in this regard, to protect the rights, freedoms and legal interests of minors, to deprive them of

parental rights or to deprive them of parental rights special attention should be paid to the effective use of the practice of submitting lawsuits to the courts.

Also in the command above:

- checking the effectiveness of the activities of the regional interdepartmental commissions on juvenile affairs and the results achieved, as well as the coordination of the activities of the competent bodies at least once every six months,
- the legality of the legal documents adopted by regional interdepartmental commissions for minors, the center of secondary special and vocational education of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education and their sub-structures, as well as local state authorities on matters of guardianship and sponsorship is determined to be studied every quarter.

The participation of prosecutor's offices in ensuring the quality and efficiency of education in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions and the main issues that should be paid attention to by them are listed below one by one.

In particular, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 140 dated March 15, 2017 "On approval of the regulation on general secondary education" and "On approval of state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" dated April 6, 2017 and other new on the basis of normative documents:

- based on the requirements of the national personnel training program, pedagogues operate according to the new state educational standards and curricula;
- training sessions are conducted by teachers with the necessary knowledge and expertise using modern information and communication technologies;
- that primary education is aimed at forming the basis of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for obtaining general secondary education, while complying with the legal requirement that children be admitted to the first grade of a general education school at the age of six or seven;
- according to the state education standard, students are fully trained in the specified subjects, the state of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in the subjects;
- participation of general education school students in classes, meaningful organization of their free time, involvement in various clubs and sports activities;
- the measures taken to increase the efficiency of education and study, the analysis of the indicators of students who are evasive, difficult to master, and whose education is difficult and preventive, and experienced teachers are assigned to them;
- the employment of persons whose right to engage in pedagogical activities or educational institutions is limited based on a court decision;
- compliance with the norms of the number of students in general education schools, authenticity of certificates issued to graduates;
- situation of upgrading and retraining of pedagogues-employees, timely filling of vacancies with qualified pedagogues;
- Methodological support and organization of district (city) public education activities, guidance of students to the profession and effectiveness of psychological and pedagogical diagnosis centers;
- that students are supported in choosing the direction of education in an academic lyceum or vocational college, taking into account their abilities, professional interests and skills;

- purposeful use of budget funds allocated to educational institutions, state of preservation of state property, effective and reasonable use of it, inspections conducted by financial authorities and legality of measures taken in this regard;
- complete and high-quality completion of construction and assembly works in newly built and renovated general education schools, authenticity of completed works;
- continuous monitoring of the fulfillment of obligations under the contract agreements concluded for the construction, capital reconstruction and repair of secondary schools;
- renovation and capital reconstruction of general education school buildings and engineering-communication infrastructure, equipping with modern teaching-laboratory equipment, computer equipment, textbooks, including electronic textbooks, and teaching-methodical materials;
- condition of sports fields and halls in secondary schools, provision of necessary equipment, trainers and other sports equipment, condition of children's health improvement;
- organization of information resource centers, provision of them with technical means and equipment, purposeful use of library funds, provision of educational literature and textbooks created on the basis of educational standards to students;
- level of provision of general education schools with modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment, electronic textbooks and teaching-methodical materials, their modernity and suitability for work and their use in practice;
- provision of basic guaranteed services for secondary schools to enter the "ZiyoNET" network;
- the presence of special qualifications of teaching staff teaching and teaching laboratory equipment and computer technology;
- free textbooks and a set of educational tools for elementary school and students with disabilities, as well as providing children from low-income families with winter clothing;
- legality of collection of funds for provision of paid services, rental of buildings and fixed assets, repair work and other purposes in educational institutions;
- the legality of spending incomes in the amount of parents' fees for child support in extended day groups in educational institutions;
- full and timely payment of salaries of pedagogues and managers of public education institutions according to basic tariff rates for each position and qualification category;
- the legality of giving wages, advances, incentives and vacation money to pedagogues, setting bonuses for teachers at the expense of the director's fund;
- funds of the director's fund are directed to encourage teachers who have made a great personal contribution to the educational process, shown loyalty and initiative to their profession, and high professional level;
- the legitimacy of additional payment to teachers for class management and checking notebooks and written works;
- legality and reasonableness of the orders and other legal documents adopted by the directors of educational institutions, the decisions of the pedagogic council, the state of reception of citizens, consideration of their appeals;
- the target spending of the budget funds allocated for the payment of teachers' work and their financial incentives should be studied based on the comparison of accounting documents and the analysis of information obtained from additional sources.

References:

1. [Electronic resource]: <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/uz/press-releases/ozbekistondagi-talim-sifatini-oshirish-imkoniyatlari>. (application time: 15.06.2023).
2. <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/uz/press-releases/ozbekistondagi-talim-sifatini-oshirish-imkoniyatlari>
3. [Electronic resource]: <https://www.norma.uz>. (application time: 15.06.2023).
4. Рахимов Ф.Х. Прокурор назорати ва унинг йўналишлари: илмий-амалий мақолалар тўплами // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Бош прокуратурасининг Олий ўқув курслари / ю.ф.д. Т.А.Умаров умумий таҳрири остида. – Т.: “Ношир” нашриёти, 2008. – Б. 115.